

Full analysis of the empirical data on Youth Assembly meeting 2 on the GreenComp

The GreenSCENT Youth Assemblies convened on November 17th and 18th 2022 in a 3-hour workshop meeting, to give valuable feedback and help co-create the GreenComp with the experts from UNINETTUNO.

DBT facilitated and organized the workshop, while UNINETTUNO presented the GreenComp and helped the participants with clarifying questions during the meeting. The workshop was divided into several sections described below.

The Youth Assembly acted as an expert panel by providing guidance, innovative ideas, and constructive feedback on the first version of the GreenComp, presented both as the Octagon (s. 26) and the Obsidian web page. This is the full analysis of the feedback given on the workshop.

Part 1: Green Skills

During the meeting, participants reflected on their everyday contribution to the green transition, and their abilities to achieve political influence. They reflected on which skills they need to learn, to gain political influence or to make a difference in their day-to-day lives. The participants described 4 competences or needs for knowledge, that can be incorporated in the GreenComp or in the pilots developed in the GreenSCENT project.

The answers suggest that partners in the GreenSCENT project need to consider if these 4 subjects are covered in the competence framework or in the learning programs in general:

1. The youth wish to obtain convincing knowledge about the green transition, to be able to change other peoples' minds about the importance of the green transition.
2. The youth want to learn how to make a green change in day-to-day life.
3. The youth need competencies to use social media as a way of spreading the word of the green transition
4. The youth want to learn how to use activism, organize protests, and demonstrations to gain political influence.

Part 2: GreenComp Competence areas (The Octagon)

The participants shared their thoughts on the competencies described in the Octagon. They worked in groups of interest, and each participant shared their feedback on two different competencies. All competencies received feedback in the process.

SMART MOBILITY	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- The participants find the competencies relevant.- They are critical of the coherence between headline and competencies.- They point out that the competencies should be formulated in a way that relates them directly to mobility or transportation. Or that the headline is altered.- The participants find 1.1 and 1.2 broad and state that they can be used in all competencies.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Conscious use of transport (walk if possible)- Green energy and life quality; why it is important to have smart mobility.- Consequences on urban communities without access to smart mobility
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- They are unsure about what 'critical thinking,' 'Equity,' 'Monitoring and learning' and 'exploiting the opportunities' means in this context.

BIODIVERSITY	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the competencies relevant and important to learn, but ask for easier/more intuitive words
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water Flora - Water fauna - How to slow down extinction
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants especially find competencies 4.2 and 2.1 important to learn.

CIRCULAR ECONOMY	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the competencies relevant and important. - The participants find Circular economy particularly important in the green transition and see it as a solution to many of the other competency areas. - 5.5 was difficult to understand to some of the participants
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The importance of digital tools in the CE - Energy coming from natural resources - Promotion of the local products to increase the local economy - Planned obsolescence - Shift away from the take-make-waste - Examples from other countries/cities which successfully implemented a circular economy
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants especially find these competencies important to learn: 1.4, 1.5, 4,2.
Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the new business model? Any exact model?

ZERO POLLUTION	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the competencies relevant and important to learn but ask for easier/more intuitive words. - The participants find it hard to understand 1.3; System thinking - The participants suggest that 1.4 is specified a bit more, e.g., what transdisciplinary means in terms of zero pollution)
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Better solutions for plastic - Better cleaner energy and technological improvements - Waste and improving waste management
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants point to the importance of these competencies: 1.1, 1.2 - 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9

GREEN BUILDINGS	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the competencies relevant. - The participants find 1.1, 1.2 and 1.3 difficult to understand in the context, and ask for clarification.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AI – to regulate consumption of electronics - Hydrogen plant - New technologies - Integrated new and old buildings - Change the pant - New materials
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the 2.1, 3.1, 3.2, and 4.3 the most important to learn.

CLEAN ENERGY	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the competencies relevant, and positively point out that it touches upon both personal and societal engagement, as well as both economy and strategy. - They point out that 1.3 Collaboration is a broad concept, and that they have not heard of 1.2 system thinking before.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Something regarding availability in the remote locations, - The participants want to learn about how to choose profitable energies, depending on the place you live. - They want to learn about the mistakes of the system we live in, and have a ethical consumption/production mentality. -
Most important competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Responsible consumption and production are particularly important as it avoid waste, which is one of the biggest issues.

CLIMATE CHANGE	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find most of the competencies relevant but find it too complicated to understand the competencies. - They point out that some of the competencies are too general, e.g., 3.1, 4.2. - They point out that some of the competencies are too complicated or unclear, e.g., 6.2, 7.1. - They point out that some seem repetitive and could be simplified into one point, e.g., 4.1 and 4.2. And 2.2, and 3.1.
Proposed competencies/Questions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - How do we make just adaptation and handle the different catastrophes related to climate change? - Who will pay, the people it hit or the people who create the problem? (E.g., Should the global north pay for the damage from floodings in Sudan and Pakistan?) - How should vulnerable areas be protected? (Often poor places in the world, who will pay for the protection) - Should there be a global price on co2 emissions, where the money will go to adaptation and rebuilding? - How do we inform people in the global south about climate change? - How do we transform the knowledge we have on climate change into action? - Should we spend a lot of time adapting to the changing climate, or should we try to stop it from changing?

FROM FARM TO FORK	
General impression	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The participants find the theme particularly important in the green transition and find that it is an effective way that consumers/lay citizens can influence the green transition, if they have the knowledge. - They find the subject hard to understand if they have not studied before. - They suggest that some of the competencies are a bit unclear, e.g., 2.2. - They find that 3.3 and 1.3 could be merged into one and presented more precisely put together. - They find 1.2 complicated to understand.
Proposed competencies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water irrigation - Promotion of local products to increase the local economy - They ask for a focus on the difference between developed and underdeveloped countries – for instance regarding the privileges that citizens in developed countries have.

Connections between competencies:

Reference: [Mural YA4](#)

Part 3: Appearance on the GreenComp web page

The participants individually explored the GreenComp web page and answered yes/no questions, guiding them to get an overview of the framework.

Questions	Yes	No	Comments
Do you think the background should be black or white?	18 (black)	24 (White)	
Do you like the 'START HERE' page?	28	8	
Do you prefer the table of content on the right side or the left?	20 (left)	20 (right)	
Do you prefer pictures or no pictures?	35	1	

Do you think the explanation of 'competence', 'knowledge', 'skills', and 'attitudes' is clear?	34	6	It could be explained more comprehensibly, to ensure that more people will understand it.
Do you think the explanation of EQF levels is clear?	23	12	
General comments			Some of the participants find the site is a bit overwhelming and ask for a 'light' version. Some participants find the design nice but the instructions are unclear and confusing.

Part 4: Appearance and usability of the GreenComp web page

The participants explored the GreenComp web page in groups of 4-5 participants. They answered questions regarding the GreenComp, which encouraged the participants to share innovative ideas, questions, and constructive feedback.

What do you think of the clarity of the 'start here' page?	The participants find that the text makes sense, it is easy to navigate, but it could use some improvements: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the 'start here' page should be on top of the list in the left navigation panel - Make the title bigger - Make the 'start here' page the front page when the web page opens - More pictures - Less links
If needed, what would improve the explanation of the EQF levels is clear?	Some of the participants find the information well balanced, while others suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explain/introduce what EQF level means, and why it is important. - Gather the information on one page, rather than in many. - Use pictures or real-life examples to increase understanding.
If needed, what would improve the explanation of the word 'competence' and 'knowledge', 'skills', and 'attitudes' is clear?	Some of the participants find the explanations meaningful, while other suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use easier words, - Use pictures - Make it clear and simpler.
What do you think of the general usability of the GreenCOMP in Obsidian?	The participants find Obsidian useful, but complicated. They suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More space between the titles, - Better organization of the main contents, e.g., make a drop menu, instead of all the subtitles. - More colors - Less color on the links, e.g., only the number is colored to show it is a link, instead of the number and the words.
What do you think about the additional categories that emerged?	The participants find the emerged categories confusing; they suggest: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Introduce the categories or summarize the ideas behind the categories. - Remove the Wikipedia links.

<p>Do you identify relations between the competencies described in the framework? (You can use the octagon to show the relations).</p>	<p>The participants have some suggestions for improvement:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It should be easier to read the competencies when you have the mind map open. It should be simplified. - The octagon is helpful for understanding the competencies better. It could be used on the web page. - Add colors.
<p>What can in your opinion improve the competence framework in general?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The web site needs improvement in organization, - Colors and pictures to show connections, and to make it more appealing - Better outlook, more user-friendly and less information.
<p>Other things or thoughts you want to share?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Simplify and summarize (as described before) - Add a subtopic to describe how the public can use the web page and collaborate with the project - Leave some more space between competencies - Older computers have a problem loading the page.